

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

A Study of the Principal's Leadership Role on Teacher's Performance in Tonra State Senior High School 1, Bone Regency of the South Sulawesi Province, Indonesia.

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine the effect of the Principal's leadership role on teacher's performance, as well as an analysis of the teacher's performance at the Tonra 1 Tonra District Bone School Bone Regency of the South Sulawesi Province, Indonesia. In conducting this research, samples were gathered with the non-probalitas data collection sample. Questionnaires, documentation, and interviews were also other method used. Descriptive and correlation techniques were used to analysis the collected data. The results showed that the principal's leadership role towards the school teachers is democratic in nature. Data analyzed showed that the principal is always known for paying attention to the teacher's welfare and school development. The teacher's performance description is rated satisfactory. This is because of the level of discipline exhibited by the school teachers during working hours, their high level of preparation with learning tools, and the implementation and completion of school activities. Thus, the school principal's high leadership skill affects the teacher's productivity which in turn helped increase the quality of education.

Keywords *leadership, school principal, teacher performance.*

INTRODUCTION

A school is a complex and unique organization, consisting of several people in order to achieve the vision and mission, so it requires a high level of coordination (Yta 2020). The human resource factor is the factor with the biggest role in achieving

organizational goals. This is due to the human factor as determining the direction of policy and implementing directly the achievement of organizational goals.

Performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities, in the context of achieving the objectives of the organization concerned legally, does not violate the law and is in accordance with morals and ethics (Awaru & Syukur, 2019; Syukur et al., 2019, Yta 2015; Yta 2020). Good performance can be seen from teachers who are disciplined in teaching attendance, teachers teach using teaching plans, and use varying codes according to the subject matter, conduct teaching evaluations and follow up on evaluation results, because teacher performance is mostly associated with poor quality of education. Teachers as social beings also need other needs to be able to work well. To be able to think and work optimally in their work, teachers are greatly influenced by the work environment in which teachers and school principals are professional (Asmanurhidayani et al., 2018; Daraba et al., 2018; Pratiwi et al., 2019).

Effective Principal's leadership will influence the participation of subordinates to do what they are responsible for by feeling satisfied and working according to the context of being able to provide vision, create a big picture, set clear and mutually agreed goals, monitor and analyze achievements and be able to develop the achievements of the student's subordinates namely by giving direction and guidance, training and mentoring and providing feedback. The leadership style used by school principals in dealing with subordinates is task-oriented and task-oriented and teacher-style styles. Principals who have an orientation to their subordinates try to motivate and not control, encouraging subordinates to carry out their tasks by letting them participate in decisions that affect them, forming friendly relations.

A school principal as the top manager at school will always try to advance the school he leads. Therefore he must have the abilities and skills related to the implementation of his duties. According to (Bare et al., 2019; Ishak, Niswaty & Guntur 2020) there are three kinds of skills as follows conceptual skills, humanitarian skills and technical skills. The same opinion was expressed by Winardi "conceptual skills, skills between human relationships or skills between individuals and technical skills". Another opinion was expressed by (Akib et al., 2016) that performance is the work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities to achieve the objectives of the organization in accordance with morals and ethics.

Performance is the level of success of a person or group of people in carrying out their duties and responsibilities as well as the ability to achieve goals and standards that have been set (Dharma & Akib, 2004; Enor & Chime 2014). From some of the explanations about the notion of performance above it can be concluded that teacher performance is the result of work done by the teacher in carrying out the tasks and responsibilities given with maximum results using effective time.

Performance is very important to be considered and evaluated because the teacher has professional assignments, meaning that the tasks can only be done with specific competencies obtained through educational programs. Teachers have broad

responsibilities that can be grouped, namely the teacher as: (1) instructor, (2) supervisor, and (3) class, administrator.

The results of observations by researchers at the State Senior High School (SMA) 1 Tonra, Bone, the implementation of leadership are not in accordance with what is expected. This is evident from the habits of the school principal when monitoring only the circumference of the classroom without ensuring that class conditions and the principal are less responsive to the problems faced by teachers so that they appear to be unwise in decision making. In relation to the Principal's leadership with the teacher's performance that the leader is responsible for directing the duties of his teacher and the leader must also provide examples and understanding to his subordinates.

Therefore, to obtain the quality of education in accordance with the objectives set, the teacher is required to always have high performance. Starting from the background, the researchers intend to research the Effect of Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance in the State Senior High School 1 Tonra, Bone Regency. As has been done by (Septiani et al., 2019) the Leadership Role of the Head of MTs Patra Mandiri Plaju to improve the performance of his teachers is in addition to providing regular salaries every month, also given some incentives and additional income outside salary. In addition to providing some incentives and additional income, the school principal also works closely with the school supervisors/supervisors to conduct professional supervision of teacher performance and supervision of classroom administration.

The results of the study from (Nasila & Akib, 2014) also state that there is an influence of leadership style for school principals on teacher performance. The aspects that play a role in the leadership of the school principal and the way the teacher works are with the desire and understanding of teachers to improve their performance and the teacher is ready to be guided to create high-capacity educational weights. The principal supports the participation of teachers in KKG activities. Researcher Hendriady (Amanurhidayani et al., 2019) also stated that Principal leadership can also motivate teachers and school culture and affect teacher performance by 82.4%.

METHOD

This research was conducted using descriptive analysis and correlation analysis. Descriptive analysis is used to find out an overview of the education level of 1 Tonra High School (SMA) teachers, and to find a picture of the performance of teachers in 1 Tonra High School (SMA). Correlation analysis is used to determine the effectiveness of the principal's leadership skilled on teacher performance in the Tonra 1 Tonra District Bone School.

The population of this study is the whole teacher in the Public High School (SMA) 1 Tonra Bone Regency in 2017. It is a limited population totaling twenty-one (21) people. In this study, researchers used sampling with a type of nonprobalitas sample, meaning that members of the population are not given the same opportunity or opportunity to be made or chosen to be a member of the sample. So the sample was chosen based on certain criteria or qualifications of twenty-one (21) people. The research instruments were divided into three parts, namely: (1) questionnaire instrument, (2) documentation instrument, and (3) interview instrument.

For data collection, this study used three ways - questionnaire instrument, instrument documentation, and interview instruments. The collected data will be analyzed using descriptive techniques and correlation techniques (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Implementation of Leadership

In every organization the implementation of leadership basically flows from top to bottom or from superiors to subordinates, so too is the Public High School (SMA) 1 Tonra in Bone Regency, where the highest leadership is tiered down to the level down to the level of subordinates to the lowest level.

The results of the interview with the Principal of the Tonra 1 High School in the District of Bone as follows:

- a. The Principal's Leadership in the 1 Tonra High School according to our observations is very democratic and always pay attention to the development of the School for the improvement of the Quality of Education in the State 1 Tonra High School
- b. The Principal acts as the School Manager, he is the Fully Responsible Manager of the extracurricular activities and school administration activities
- c. The Principal's leadership in SMA Negeri 1 Tonra is the ability of the principal to influence its members to make an effort to achieve a planned goal.
- d. The implementation of leadership described as stated earlier is limited to indicators or that is decision making and providing work motivation.

a. Decision-making

To describe the principal's attitude towards providing opportunities for teachers the teacher submits a proposal or idea before deciding a meeting in the following table:

Table 1

Respondents response to the opportunity to submit ideas at a Meeting

No	Respondents' Answers	amount	%
1	Never	3	14.29
2	Sometimes	6	28.57
3	Always	12	57.14
Amount		21	100

Source: Processed from questionnaires, 2018.

Based on the answers of respondents in the table above, it shows that the principal's leadership role in providing opportunities for teachers/participants of the meeting to submit ideas or proposals are classified as high. Furthermore, that. To describe the principal's attitude towards acceptance or treatment of proposals or ideas submitted by the teacher at each meeting, it can be seen in the table below.

Table 2

Respondents 'Responses to Principals' Attitudes

No	Respondents' Answers	amount	%
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1	Not responding	-	-
2	Not Responding	9	42.86
3	Always Respond	12	57.14
Amount		21	100

Source: Processed from questionnaires, 201 8

Based on the respondents' answers in the table above shows that the principal's attitude in responding to every idea or proposal submitted by meeting participants was sufficient. In any decision-making process that involves the teacher and the teacher, of course, prioritizes deliberation to reach consensus or the decision taken can be mutually agreed upon by all meeting participants. To describe the attitude of the principal if he does not reach the consensus at a meeting, it can be seen in the following table:

Table 3

Respondents 'Responses to School Principals' Attitudes if the meeting does not reach consensus

No	Respondents' Answers	amount	%
1	Not Taking Decisions	2	9.52
2	Postpone Decision Making	7	33.33
3	Vote	12	57.15
Amount		21	100

Source: Processed from questionnaires, 201 8

Based on the answers of respondents in the table above shows that the principal's leadership if in a meeting can not reach the word consensus is good. Decision making through voting is the most democratic step that can be taken if a decision cannot be reached through consensus. While the lobby is done if the decision to be taken is considered safe, and does not cause a gap either to the organization or to the parties concerned.

b. Provision of Work Motivation

The leadership of the Head of the State Senior High School 1 Tonra Bone Regency in terms of providing work motivation can be seen in the following table:

Table 4

Respondents Response to Granting Praise or appreciation

No	Respondents' Answers	amount	%
1	Never	10	47.62
2	Sometimes	7	33.33
3	Often	4	19.05
Amount		21	100

Source: Processed from questionnaires, 2018

Based on the answers of respondents in the table above shows that the leadership of school principals in giving praise or appreciation to teachers or teachers who have

achievements in carrying out their duties properly is inadequate. Efforts to motivate teachers and teachers are not limited to giving praise or appreciation for the successful implementation of the task as a form of motivating subordinates. However, it is also equally important if paying attention to completing a task or job.

To describe efforts to guide teachers or teachers who have difficulty carrying out their duties can be seen in the table below.

Table 5
 Respondents' Responses to Guidance
 that given the principal

No	Respondents' Answers	Amount	%
1	Never	10	47.62
2	Sometimes	7	33.33
3	Often	4	19.05
amount		21	100

Source: Processed from questionnaires, 2018

Based on respondents' answers in the table above indicate that the principal effort to motivate the form of guidance to teachers and teachers who have difficulty doing a good job has been goodwill but not maximized. Then to describe the efforts of principals in motivating teachers and teachers by providing moral support if a disaster strikes, can be seen in the following table.

Table 6
 Respondents' Responses to Moral Giving
 for teachers who have been hit by disaster

No	Respondents' Answers	amount	%
1	Never	-	-
2	Sometimes	6	28.57
3	Often	15	71.43
Amount		21	100

Source: Processed from questionnaires, 2018

Based on the answers of respondents in the table above shows that the principal's leadership in motivating subordinates by giving moral support to the teacher if there is a high category of disaster. In addition to providing guidance and moral support, motivation can also be achieved by giving actions to teachers and teachers who violate rules or rules that have been set in accordance with the violations committed. This effort is another form of motivation to avoid the things that can harm the organization and the teacher.

The performance of the teacher

The results of interviews with respondents about teacher performance are as follows:

Overview Teacher Performance in high school, which teachers have had a good performance according to standards As knowledge held by teachers is in accordance with the subject's requirements, the skills and attitudes the teachers possess are good enough to socialize with students in a school community.

Likewise with the results of interviews with other respondents about teacher performance revealed that performance can be assessed at three stages, namely: Preparation of completeness of Learning Tools, Student Absences, Educational Calendar and etc. Implementation of Classroom PBM, Learning Methods, Proposing material, and Use of Learning Media, as well as evaluation/reflection, conducting assessment and reflection.

The working conditions of teachers in this study are limited to matters relating to discipline during working hours, discipline in the implementation and completion of school work.

a. Discipline during Business Hours

Discipline at the time of entry, rest time and after school hours is a manifestation of the teacher's responsibility to carry out the assignment within the allotted time, or if it is logical that a teacher arrives at school on time and immediately performs his work, likewise his return time is considered that whenever the teacher goes home at the specified time means he has filled the time to complete the task properly.

To get a description of the discipline of teachers regarding the provisions of teaching hours, can be seen in the following table.

Table 7

Respondents' Responses to Terms of Teaching Admission

No.	Respondents' Answers	amount	%
1	Do not follow	-	-
2	Sometimes	7	33.33
3	Often	14	66.67
	Amount	21	100

Source: Processed from Questionnaire, 2018

Based on the answers of respondents in the table above shows the level of discipline of the teacher the condition of the performance of the teachers of the State Senior High School 1 Tonra Bone Regency in the hours of teaching entry is very high.

Based on interviews with some respondents entered school yet because before his teacher's first child drove her to school, and there is also a teacher whose house to school far enough away so it is not possible to teach timely. Then to describe the level of teacher discipline in the provisions of the break time can be seen in the following table.

Table 8

Respondents' Responses to Break Time Conditions

No.	Respondents' Answers	amount	%
1	Before recess	-	-
2	After the task is complete	9	42.86
3	According to the break	12	57.14
	amount	21	100

Source: Processed from Questionnaire, 2018

Based on the answers of respondents in the table above shows that the discipline of teachers during recess is relatively high.

b. Discipline on the Implementation and Completion of Tasks

To find out the level of discipline of teachers in carrying out and completing assignments in the State Senior High School 1 Tonra Bone Regency can be seen in the following table.

Table 9

Respondents' responses to school work completion

No.	Respondents' Answers	amount	%
1	Never on time	3	14.28
2	Sometimes on time	6	28.57
3	Always on time	12	57.14
	Amount	21	100

Source: Processed from Questionnaire, 2018

Based on the answers of respondents in the table above shows that the level of discipline of teachers in completing official tasks on time is high.

The influence of the Principal's leadership on the performance.

Based on the results of interviews with respondents about the Principal's leadership of the teacher's work, it was revealed that the Principal had a great influence on Teacher Performance, the Principal periodically conducted a Teacher Performance Assessment, examined Learning Tools, carried out Class Supervision, and monitored the teacher's attendance on time.

The results of interviews with other respondents about the leadership of the School Principal on teacher performance are the Positive Behavior of the Principal to motivate the Teacher to work together with the Group and the environment, teacher work performance is getting better because the Principal is always trying to explore, utilize and enhance the creativity of its members to achieve high achievement.

Factors that cause the high and low performance of teachers in the implementation of tasks and work in conditions of performance of school teachers on the performance of teachers of the State Senior High School 1 Tonra in addition to highly dependent on the leading factors that are applied and developed by the leadership, also influenced by several factors among others:

a. Teacher Psychological Motivation

Teacher psychological motivation is a psychological process that occurs in a person that reflects the interaction between attitudes, needs, perceptions and decisions that occur in a person.

b. Fulfillment of Needs (Welfare)

The welfare of life is every human's dream. Likewise, the teacher as a person also wants a decent level of welfare. The intended level of welfare is the amount of salary or wages received causing them to live properly in the sense that primary needs are properly fulfilled and can also save a portion of their income to prepare for the future.

Concrete steps certainly need to be pursued by the central government to improve teacher salaries at a level that allows teachers to live a more decent life because the feasibility of life is one aspect that can give pleasure to live and will affect concentration in carrying out tasks and jobs properly.

c. Habit

Habit is one of the factors that influence the level of teacher discipline. Even though a teacher is given motivation from the direct supervisor and the fulfillment of his needs has been fulfilled, but they are accustomed to being late to school and leaving school early will certainly affect the efficiency and effectiveness of the implementation and completion of tasks / official work. This is one of the factors that can hamper the implementation and completion of tasks/work because it is not disciplined. So the habit of arriving late and leaving school early must be observed for the sake of smooth work that is the responsibility of every teacher.

CONCLUSION

The conclusions from the results of research and discussion have been described as follows: 1) The performance of teachers in the State High School (SMA) 1 Tonra in Bone Regency has been satisfactory, this can be seen from the preparation of the completeness of the Learning Tools and discipline during working hours, discipline in the implementation and completion of school work. 2) The influence of the Principal's leadership on the performance of teachers in the State Senior High School 1 Tonra Bone Regency mostly affects the performance of teachers so that by itself there is also created a high-performance improvement and improvement in Education Quality.

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